

STAFFING FORMATION IN THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY

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Abstract

The authors aim to substantiate approaches to staff training in the hospitality industry. It is assumed that the management of the processes of prospecting, recruiting and hiring personnel, is the key to a company's success in the market of such a promising area such as the hotel industry. We identified that the personnel system of the hotel business in the Russian Federation is still in formation and requires significant efforts to coordinate the quantitative and qualitative levels of training of new specialists with the needs of hotel companies. It is evidenced in this study that the detailed analysis of the characteristics of the operation and personnel of the hotel industry, which will allow to determine the paths of development of the industry and make the transition to a higher level of development. It is found, therefore, that the most important task in solving the existing problems, in Human Resource Management in the tourism sector currently in Russia, is the search for new approaches to recruitment based on a modern concept of recruitment from contemporary management in modern enterprises.

Keywords: Management; System; Recruitment; Technology; Hotel business.

ORMAÇÃO DE PESSOAL NA INDÚSTRIA DE HOSPITALIDADE

Resumo

Os autores procuram substanciar as abordagens à formação de pessoal na indústria hoteleira. Parte-se do princípio de que a gestão dos processos de prospecção, recrutamento e contratação de pessoal, é a chave para o sucesso de uma empresa no mercado de uma área tão promissora como a indústria hoteleira. Identificamos que o sistema de pessoal do negócio hoteleiro na Federação Russa ainda está em formação e requer esforços significativos para coordenar os níveis quantitativos e qualitativos de formação de novos especialistas com as necessidades das empresas hoteleiras. Evidencia-se neste estudo que a análise detalhada das características do funcionamento e do pessoal da indústria hoteleira, que permitirá determinar as vias de desenvolvimento da indústria e fazer a transição para um nível superior de desenvolvimento. Verifica-se, portanto, que a tarefa mais importante na resolução dos problemas existentes, na Gestão de Recursos Humanos no setor de turismo atualmente na Rússia, é a procura de novas abordagens de recrutamento baseadas num conceito moderno de gestão de recrutamento nas empresas contemporâneas.

Palavras-chave: Gestão; Sistema; Recrutamento; Tecnologia; Hotelaria.

FORMACIÓN DE PERSONAL EN LA INDUSTRIA DE LA HOSPITALIDAD

Resumen

Los autores tratan de fundamentar los enfoques de la formación del personal en el sector de la hostelería. Se supone que la gestión de los procesos de prospección, reclutamiento y contratación de personal, es la clave del éxito de una empresa en el mercado de un área tan prometedora como la industria hotelera. Identificamos que el sistema de personal de la hostelería en la Federación Rusa está todavía en formación y requiere esfuerzos importantes para coordinar los niveles cuantitativos y cualitativos de la formación de nuevos especialistas con las necesidades de las empresas hoteleras. Se pone de manifiesto en este estudio que el análisis detallado de las características del funcionamiento y del personal de la industria hotelera, que permitirá determinar las vías de desarrollo de la industria y hacer la transición a un mayor nivel de desarrollo. Por lo tanto, se constata que la tarea más importante en la solución de los problemas existentes, en la Gestión de Recursos Humanos en el sector turístico actualmente en Rusia, es la búsqueda de nuevos enfoques de contratación basados en un concepto justificado de gestión de la contratación en las empresas modernas de la industria hotelera.

Palabras clave: Gestión; Sistema; Contratación; Tecnología; Hostelería.

1 INTRODUCTION

The search for effective ways to overcome the economic crisis, accelerate the rate of formation of market relations, the growth in the number of profitable hotel businesses necessitate the use of not only

organizational, administrative, financial, and management measures, commercial software in the hotel business management system but also the expansion of the practice of using scientifically substantiated methods and technologies (Melián-Alzola et al., 2020).

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In the practice of sectoral staffing, on the one hand, the qualitative composition of the professional qualification structure is deteriorating, not enough attention is paid to training, the system of continuing education, including for managers and specialists, does not meet modern requirements.

On the other hand, at all levels of management, there is an inconsistency in the interaction of spontaneous and regulatory factors of the market mechanism, most managers and specialists lack the necessary experience and knowledge on the competent use of available resources, internal talent, the formation of a competitive and professional-qualification personnel structure (Student et al., 2019).

The totality of existing contradictions, the predominance of negative phenomena in the economy, and the staffing situation lead to haphazard work, failures, and disruptions in the management cycle of staffing, which increases the drop in production volumes, an increase in the number of the unemployed, and other negative processes (Rahi, 2019).

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Currently, the successful operation of the hotel business is directly related to a significant increase in the efficiency of using production resources and an increase in staff productivity. At the same time, the orientation of the hotel business to market relations changes the approaches to solving economic problems, primarily those that are directly related to human resources (Rasool et al., 2019).

The general management paradigm is also changing significantly. At present, personnel is seen as the main resource of a hotel business that determines the success of all activities, a resource that one must manage properly, create optimal conditions for its development, spending the necessary funds on this. At the same time, proper qualified management of personnel and other resources of the hotel business ensures the achievement of the necessary economic result (Sofronov, 2018).

Agaveva notes that one of the main criteria for the development of a hotel enterprise is staffing. The scholar emphasizes that the high level of a hotel enterprise depends on the appropriate qualifications of its staff, its motivation, teamwork, discipline, and ability and desire to learn (2017).

Barilo emphasizes that, subject to proper staffing, a hotel company can reach the top but the wrong choice of employees can adversely affect the results of the hotel company, and sometimes it will even be forced to stop working (2020).

The essence of the organization of staffing in the hotel management system lies in the fact that people

are considered the property of the hotel enterprise. Consequently, the performance of any hotel largely depends on the qualification of decisions in the system of selection, placement, movement, training, and promotion of employees. Therefore, it is necessary, first of all, to determine the essence of the economic category "personnel".

According to Kuptsova (2016), personnel are full-time qualified employees with certain professional training who have special knowledge, work skills, or work experience in the chosen field of activity (p. 61).

The term "personnel" in scientific sources is often identified only with a part of the employees, namely, highly qualified specialists or workers with work experience at a particular enterprise (Selezneva et al., 2019, p. 154).

Khatikova notes that the staff is the main resource, the effectiveness of the use of which largely determines the results of the hotel enterprise and its competitiveness. Employees set material elements in motion and create a hotel product, cost, and surplus product in the form of profit (2020).

Churkina (2017) understands staffing as a set of actions aimed at finding, evaluating, and establishing predetermined relationships with the workforce both in the hotel enterprise itself for further career advancement and outside it for new hiring of temporary or permanent workers.

Despite sufficient attention to the problem of staffing in the hospitality industry, the issues of normalizing and forecasting employment in the hotel business, improving the staffing mechanism, and further training for those employed in the service sector remained insufficiently developed (Theron et al., 2018). There is also a need for additional research to improve the setting of priorities in the staffing system of the hotel business.

3 METHODS

The study was carried out based on Plekhanov Russian University of Economics, Moscow State University of Sport and Tourism, Amur State University and Moscow Polytechnic University in 2021-2022.

The methodological framework of the study contained the following general scientific methods: analysis and synthesis with the analysis of existing theoretical and methodological approaches and provisions, scientific developments on the problems of personnel training for the hospitality industry; the structural and logical method in the systematization of factors affecting the state of the hotel business.

The selection of sources was carried out considering the current state of the hospitality industry. We used legislative and regulatory legal acts, materials

of state and local authorities, academic publications by Russian and foreign scholars on the problems of staffing in the hospitality industry (Lukiyanchuk, et al., 2020; Ogloblina, et al., 2017). We paid special attention to scientific articles concerning the research problem.

During the study, we plan to develop approaches to analyzing the problems of personnel training for the hospitality industry, substantiate the strategies of the behavior of participants in the hotel business in the labor market. Moreover, we set out to substantiate approaches to assessing the quality of the education system, identify and formulate the main directions for

the development of the hotel business in the context of digitalization.

4 RESULTS

Practice has shown that staffing management is an integral part of managing the hotel business. It is aimed at, first meeting the needs of the hotel business in qualified personnel, and second, at ensuring a high level of employment of the working-age population and its optimal distribution and has certain principles (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Recruitment principles at hospitality industry enterprises.

Source: own elaboration.

Moreover, staffing management as a system includes separate subsystems, each of which consists of a few areas and elements that are independently significant but are aimed at solving a common problem. This system is constantly evolving and improving. Therefore, at each stage, the system must be brought in line with the achieved level of development of production forces as the pace of sustainable development of the hotel business increases. Furthermore, the solution to constantly emerging problems requires making adjustments to the individual elements of the control system (Stankov, Gretzel, 2021).

At the same time, the establishment of a market economy and manufacturing practice gives rise to new tasks, the implementation of which also requires corresponding changes in the management mechanism. Studies show that the development of the hotel business in the Russian Federation and the growing competition require a constant improvement in the quality of hotel services, and there is a need to raise the requirements for all categories of hotel personnel since the quality of hotel service is primarily determined by the work of the services responsible for the state of the rooms and in direct contact with clients.

Practice has shown that the hotel business in the Russian Federation is currently suffering serious losses. First, the coronavirus pandemic stopped the usual flow of tourists for an extended period, and accommodation facilities (hotels, hotels, campsites, and hostels) were forced to temporarily stop or restrict commercial activities, and later they accepted guests only if they had an approved vaccine.

At the beginning of 2022, the strict anti-COVID bans began to weaken, and the next season promised to bring long-awaited profits to hoteliers. However, the geopolitical situation and economic sanctions imposed by the US and EU countries will again have a negative impact on the work of Russian hotels. The number of foreign tourists will decline. Due to the rise in the cost of materials, goods, and services, it will be difficult for hoteliers to open new businesses and bring them to self-sufficiency.

Under these conditions, one of the main problems in the activities of Russian hotel enterprises is the lack of job profiles, which does not allow hotels to select personnel in accordance with the necessary psychological characteristics that guarantee the compatibility of employees in the process of joint performance of work duties.

As a result, Russian hotel enterprises do not have the necessary psychological climate conducive to the desire of employees to continue working. Moreover, there are conflict situations, as a result of which some of the employees either quit or go to work in other hotel enterprises.

The need for systematic advanced training of personnel is also determined by the globalization of markets. The influence of this factor is manifested in the fact that the quality of features and service in hotels should be comparable with international standards. However, most hotel service personnel in the Russian Federation do not have special education, do not have the skills to work with modern information and hospitality technologies, or knowledge of the psychology and ethics of working with clients.

Meanwhile, the work performed by the service personnel usually does not meet modern standards of service quality. On the other hand, this part of the staff has significant work experience lacked by graduates of educational institutions. That is why the primary task of modern hotels at present is the restructuring of management methods, the formation of an efficient management policy aimed at training competent personnel.

Resorts are interested in having more and more employees with analytical thinking, capable of finding new things in their field of work. Personnel management in hotels should focus on preparing and saturating all sectors with a creatively capable workforce. After all, a modern worker should be not only professionally competent but also proactive, more independent in decision-making.

Therefore, to achieve a world level in staffing of the hospitality industry, it is necessary to investigate and solve the following main issues: test the staffing process of hotel businesses; analyze the current practice of selection, placement and certification of personnel; give a forecast estimate of the total demand for personnel, taking into account private hotels and new construction; analyze the quantitative and qualitative composition of the employees of the hospitality enterprises, considering the requirements dictated by the time, focus on qualitative changes in the level of service and increasing the effective demand of the population; define the higher education institutions that train the specialist in the hospitality industry; give an expert assessment of the compliance of the training level of a hospitality industry specialist and the requirements for a specialist in this category; carry out comparative analysis of the supply of staffing in the hotel business and the real demand for it in terms of quantitative and qualitative parameters; substantiate proposals for changing the quality structure of staffing for the hotel business and improving the level of their training.

At the same time, the scale and importance of the tasks associated with the rapid development of the hotel business in the Russian Federation require the heads of hotel businesses and government officials to develop and adopt such management documents of tactical and strategic importance that would ensure the implementation of a systematic approach to the development of the hotel business in the country as a whole and would be primarily aimed at creating and developing the internal talent of hotel businesses.

No matter how perfect the legal field, the organizational and managerial structure of hotels, the mechanism for managing hotel businesses, it is becoming increasingly obvious that the hotels that have qualified specialists in their staff are currently working with the greatest efficiency. These specialists know the specific features of the industry, have management skills, including financial management, know hotel management, including reservation systems for hotel and tourist services, and international service standards.

Practice has shown that the system of policy measures should cover the main directions of state policy in the field of training hotel business specialists in connection with the adaptation of higher education and science of the Russian Federation to the Bologna process, the introduction of a new credit-module-based system for organizing the educational process in educational institutions, making changes and additions to the list of areas and specialties where the specialists are trained at the corresponding educational and qualification levels.

At the same time, the system of training employees in the hotel industry is strongly associated with advanced training and has problems, including insufficient training of graduates, training of personnel with secondary vocational education due to a decrease in the plan for admission to higher educational institutions (Figure 2).

Currently, more than 300 universities are training managers of various levels for the hospitality industry in Russia. At the same time, many universities, which did not previously specialize in this area, immediately responded to the demand and opened faculties for the training of hotel business managers. The number of places where one can obtain a diploma or certificate proving knowledge in this area is growing every year.

Unfortunately, the level of training of specialists in the hospitality industry in Russia does not yet meet international standards. The training sector does not meet the needs of the hospitality industry, either quantitatively or qualitatively. Practice has shown that in Russian universities all study time is devoted to the study of theoretical foundations.

Figure 2. Main issues in training specialists for the hospitality industry.

Source: own elaboration.

In addition, the central place in the curriculum is occupied by general education subjects, and specialization begins only in the last two years of study. Unlike the Russian method of teaching hotel business, the first years of study in foreign hotel schools are devoted to practical acquaintance with the hospitality industry. Students begin to study management only in their senior years when they already know the work of hotels from the inside (Zhang et al., 2020).

It is impossible not to mention in this case the Vatel Institute, a school of international hotel and tourism management in France, which has the largest training center in Nice. Here, students can fully develop their abilities and gain extensive practical skills. On the basis of the institute, there is a functioning four-star hotel, three restaurants, and three kitchens equipped with modern equipment (Sikora, Ferris, 2014).

The second problem is practice for students of Russian universities. In most cases, hotels take students for a short period of time without pay. However, in foreign countries, students have the opportunity to undergo paid practice every academic year with the possibility of further employment in their specialization. An example is the IHTTI School of Hotel Management in Neuchâtel, Switzerland.

Moreover, the public significance of the hotel business as a significant factor in the formation of the state's economy necessitates the creation of an industry-specific system for training and advanced training of human resources. Until recently, there was no specialized tourism and hotel education in the country at all, except for several institutes for advanced training and training of guides and interpreters.

Currently, a network of educational institutions of various accreditation levels has already been formed for training personnel in the hotel business. Moreover, the restructuring of higher educational institutions at the present stage is due to a change in their social functions, the need to increase the flexibility and variability of the education system, which provides for the development of various educational institutions with

different programs and levels of training for future specialists.

The acute issues in the development of education in the hotel business still include, first of all, the quality of training of specialists, the level of curricula, methodological developments, and their adaptation to the conditions of competition in the modern market of hotel services. At the same time, the analysis of the existing system of professional development in the hotel business shows that the main problem at present, which hinders the qualitative formation and renewal of professional skills of hotel workers, is the defects in the regulatory framework.

The existing requirements for the qualifications of hotel personnel need to be improved according to world qualification standards. Moreover, the methodological support of the current system of further education in the hotel business requires significant revision due to the following typical circumstances:

- a) the structure of stages of further education does not correspond to the principles of consistency and continuity of forming and updating professional skills;
- b) as a rule, there is no methodological framework for assessing the professional development of employees within a hotel business, there are no clearly formulated, scientifically substantiated criteria for the formation of professional skills of service personnel;
- c) lack of variability, flexible approaches to the formation of the content of further education courses according to the changes in the requirements of the external environment, market conditions;
- d) the content of training does not cover all the specific features of the technology of providing hotel services, i.e. little attention is paid to the culture of service, the features of working with foreign guests, studying the psychological nuances of working with groups of tourists, taking into account ethnic characteristics;

- e) imperfection of the didactic framework of teaching;
- f) the hotel almost hardly ever uses the existing general methods and techniques for studying the motivational sphere in the system of professionalism of employees;
- g) the lack of specialists with both professional knowledge in the hotel business and psychological and pedagogical training to work with personnel in the system of further education for hotel workers.

5 DISCUSSION

Our conclusions are consistent with the results of Ince, Kendir (2016), Ye, Law (2021), Mannaa, Abou-Shouk (2020), among others. The reliability of the presented approaches is confirmed by the fact that there is an objective need to form a conceptually new approach to the training and professional development of personnel in the hotel business. At the same time, the socio-economic experience has put on the agenda the problem of creating a continuing education system for specialists in the hotel business, which would correspond to world standards (Agamirova et al., 2017; Malyugina, et al., 2020; Panasenکو, et al., 2021).

At the same time, our studies, unlike other studies (Cogin et al., 2016, Benaraba et al., 2022; Akosah-Twumasi et al., 2018), consider the factors that currently determine the development of continuing education in the hotel business include the discrepancy between the budgetary and commercial strategies for the development of hotel education; the passivity of the state education system in terms of the socio-economic and political conditions for the development of the hotel business; expanding and increasing the number of requests of various categories of service workers to create-related various educational hotel programs; the desire of some specialists to actualize their professional qualities and create their hotel educational practice; creation of an unconventional form of managing educational activities in the hotel business.

In this case, our research complements the research with the stages of creating and implementing a hotel educational system in the Russian Federation, which includes: analysis of the needs of the hotel sector; specialization of educational institutions with the availability of appropriate material support; further education of the faculty for the development of new educational materials in the hospitality industry; introduction of new training programs for the hospitality industry; involvement of hospitality enterprises in the process of introducing a new educational system; introduction of a mechanism for continuously monitoring results, which guarantees the compliance of

the educational system in the hotel business with quality standards; establishing partnerships with international training centers for the internationalization of training (Lim, 2020).

6 CONCLUSION

All in all, it can be noted that the staffing system of the hotel business in the Russian Federation is at the forming stage and requires significant effort to coordinate the quantitative and qualitative levels of training of new specialists with the needs of hotel businesses.

Currently, the scientific rationale for staffing in the hotel business can be presented in the form of the following indicators: the state of internal talent in the industry, sphere, or territory; determination of the prospects for the development of hotel businesses at various levels; development and adoption of state standards for the professional work of those employed in hotel businesses; the creation of a mechanism for professionalism certification for leading hospitality specialists; development of models for training, retraining and advanced training of specialists, fundamentally new curricula and programs, job analyses and modern methods for training specialists in the hotel business; creation of a system of practice and training for specialists at different levels; scientific and methodological support for training, retraining and advanced training of specialists in the hotel business.

At the same time, a detailed analysis of the features of the functioning and staffing of the hotel industry will make it possible to determine the development paths of the industry and make the transition to a qualitatively new level of development.

Therefore, the main task for the further development of such a promising area as the hospitality industry is to manage the processes of scouting, recruiting, and hiring personnel, which is the key to the company's success in the market.

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Table 1. CRediT author statement

Term	Definition	Author 1	A.2	A.3	A.4	A.5
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	+	+			
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models		+	+	+	
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components		+		+	+
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	+	+			+
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	+		+	+	+
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	+		+		
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools		+		+	+
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	+		+	+	
Writing – Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	+	+	+	+	+
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or post-publication stages			+		+
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	+		+		+
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team		+		+	
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	+		+		+
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	+	+	+	+	+

Source: adapted from Elsevier (2022, s/p), based upon Brand et al. (2015).

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